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Personality traits, peer influence as a correlate of Nomophobic behaviour among undergraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo university, ILE-IFE, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The study investigated the prevalence of Nomophobic behaviour among undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. It also ascertained the correlate of each of students' psychosocial factors (personality traits and peer influence) and Nomophobic behaviour among undergraduates. It examined the correlates of students' social factor (peer influence) and Nomophobic behaviour and ascertained the correlates of psychological factor (personality traits) and Nomophobic behaviour among students in the study area. These were with a view to providing information on psychosocial factors that have relationship with Nomophobic behaviour among the students.

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population for the study consisted of Obafemi Awolowo University undergraduate students. A sample of 1080 undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University was selected using multi-stage sampling technique. Six faculties out of 13 were selected using simple random sampling technique and two departments were selected from each of the six faculties using simple random sampling technique to give a total of 12 departments in all. Convenient sampling technique was used to select 90 (100 level to 400/500 level) students from each of the two departments selected in each faculty to make a total of 1080 respondents in all. One instrument titled Psychosocial and Nomophobic Behaviour among Undergraduate Students which contained five sections; Section A comprised item on students' Nomophobic behaviour, Section B, contained items on students' personality traits, and Section C comprised items on peer influence, Data collected were analyzed using percentage, Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Multiple Regression analyses.

The results showed that (83.8%) of the undergraduate students exhibited moderate level of Nomophobic behaviour. Furthermore, the results established that there was a significant relationship between each students' personality traits and Nomophobic behaviour among the students (extraversion and Nomophobic behaviour $r = 0.04$, agreeableness and Nomophobic behaviour $r = 0.12$, conscientiousness and Nomophobic behaviour $r = 0.13$, neuroticism and Nomophobic behaviour $r = 0.26$ and openness to experience and Nomophobic behaviour $r = -.01$, p -value < 0.05). The results also showed that there was significant relationship between peer influence and Nomophobic behaviour among the students with ($r = .18$, p value < 0.05). The study concluded that peer influence had the strongest relationship with Nomophobic behaviour of university undergraduates in Obafemi Awolowo University, followed by personality traits, religiosity and depression respectively.

Keywords: Nomophobic Behaviour; Peer influence; Personality Traits; Undergraduate Students

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1. Introduction

Across the world, technology seems to be an irreplaceable part of human existence because of its invaluable contributions to make the entire world to be a global village. It is not an overstatement that individuals increasingly depend on technological gadgets day in day out as it brings tranquility to the existence of human lives. Likewise, it enhances the performance of daily activities to be made easy through the use of technological devices, such as; computers, apple wrist-watches, and smart-television. Of particular interest is the use of smartphones because it enhances the flow of communication far and near without having to meet physically. Besides, individuals could build educational network through the use of different channels like facebook, twitter, whatsapp, Instagram, telegram, yahoo messenger and host of others.

Tracing back to the early stages of evolutionary history of life, communication technique was among the most important steps and telephones provided one-way contact. Despite the myriad importance of smartphones in the world of education, undergraduate students seem to exhibit Nomophobic whenever they are parted with this gadget. There is no doubt that communication technology plays a significant role in everyday life; however, the unrestrained use of the smartphone leads to the development of behavioural addictions called Nomophobic

The term Nomophobic behaviour is a modern coinage and stands for no-mobile-phone phobia. Nomophobic behaviour is a relatively new phenomenon that has become more and more popular over the last five years since the publication of the Nomophobic Questionnaire (Yildirim & Correia, 2015). Based on a public poll, the word Nomophobic behaviour has been selected the word of the year for 2018 by Cambridge dictionary (Daily Mail, 2018), exemplifying the popularity of the term in mainstream media and among the public., Yildirim and Correia's (2015) conceptualization of Nomophobic behaviour portrays it as an unintended consequence of university students' overdependence on smartphones and their capabilities.

Nomophobic is conceptualized by Cherry (2020) as the fear of being deprived of one's mobile phone. For example, some researchers see the concept of nomophobia as a useless and harmful behavioural problem because, it is the fear felt by students when they are unable to access or communicate with their mobile phone (Gezgin & cakil, 2016). However, nomophobia could be as a result of too much dependence on smartphone, due to mobile marketing and online trading in which individual engage themselves in other to make a living. However, University students are constantly interacting with information, as well as social media and other internet-based applications via their smartphones. When these applications are not available, people become anxious and nervous, as a result, their abilities to concentrate on daily activities and academics suffer (Yildirim & Correia, 2015). Likewise, different use of applications via smartphone could make life easier by making information and other means of communication accessible, but the convenience comes at a price which is Nomophobic.

Nomophobic behaviour has many comorbid disorders, two or more disorders within an individual, such as: anxiety and panic disorder, other forms of phobia (and in particular social phobia disorder), obsessive-compulsive disorder, eating disorders, any disorder under the umbrella of depression from dysthymia to major depressive disorder, alcohol and drug addiction, as well as other behavioural addiction disorders (including mobile and/or internet dependence, gambling, online gaming, compulsive shopping, and sexual behaviours) and personality disorders (borderline, antisocial, and avoiding) (Bragazzi & Puente, 2014; Clayton, 2015).

Meanwhile, the concept of nomophobia is used to describe a psychological condition when people have a fear of being detached from their mobile phone. Therefore, nomophobia could be seen as the irrational fear when individual could not reach their cell phones or Smartphones, or they could not communicate through these mobile devices (King, 2013; Yildirim & Correia, 2015).

Gezin (2017) was of the opinion that majority of undergraduate students check their phones for texts and notifications at least once during the night. Students who exhibit nomophobia may experience anxiety about losing touch with others and a sense of dependency on technology, among other things. Additionally, this may have a detrimental impact on their capacity to sleep, making it more difficult for them to learn in class the next day. According to Spitzer's (2015) technology reliance and nomophobia are to blame for the bad effects on academics and school life. Undergraduate students might feel depressed, emotionally imbalance and confused when they forget their mobile phones at their lecture theatres or hostel or even when undergraduate go out for lunch for a short time.

Though, cognitive differences could account for variances in Nomophobic behaviour. Likewise, psychosocial factors like peer pressure, religiosity and personality traits and could also account for it among undergraduate students

Peer groups are among the most influential social forces affecting undergraduate behaviour (Misanya, 2013). This is because peers play a large role in the social and emotional development of undergraduates and their Nomophobic behaviour (Allen, McGarland, & Elhaney, 2005). However, Castrogiovanni (2002) defined peer group as a small group of similar age, fairly close friends, sharing the same activities. In its most acceptable form, peer group is a healthy coming of age intermediary, by which undergraduates grasp negotiating skills and learn to deal with challenges and to solve problems in a social context and even academic. Peer group could also act as positive role model, for example, if one keeps a group of people that are ambitious and working hard to attain high academic goals, one might feel pressured to follow suit to avoid feeling excluded from the group. A negative peer influence could be seen as one of the militating forces while most students recorded poor academic performance. The reason for this is not farfetched: students spent large amount of time in extra curriculum; most especially on their smartphones. More often than not, academic priorities are neglected and thus academic performance grossly affected.

It was further suggested by Katz in Olalekan (2016) that one group might have a negative impact on its members while the other might have positive impact on its members as well. In order to know how to manage Nomophobic behaviour and people effectively, it is necessary to take into account the group that students keep and how they feel about nomophobia and their behaviour towards studies (academics). This means understanding the significance of individual differences, the characteristics of people in the group, the personality traits they possess and the type of behaviour they exhibit (Armstrong, 2009).

Personality refers to individual differences. Personality is the characteristic sets of behaviours, cognition and emotional patterns that evolve from heredity and environment. Buchanan and Huczynski (2004) defined personality as the psychological qualities that influence an individual's characteristics, behaviour patterns in a stable and distinctive manner. Ivancevich (2008), personality appeared to be organized into patterns that are to some degree, observable, measurable and involved both common and unique characteristics in which every person is different from each other person in some respects but similar to other persons in other aspects.

According to Schermerhorn, Hunt, and Osborn (2005), personality traits are persistent attributes that distinctively identify a person's conduct. Being steadfast, timid, aggressive, lethargic, ambitious, shy, assertive, opinionated, introverted, outspoken, evasive, etc. are some examples. When these characteristics are displayed frequently, it becomes a personality feature.

In other terms, if a quality is more consistent, stable, and manifests more frequently in a range of circumstances, the more relevant it is in characterizing a person. The Big Five personality qualities, social traits, personal conception traits, and emotional adjustment traits are the categories used to group personality traits. All of these characteristics influence how individuals behave in work environments and do their jobs (Sev, 2006). Costa and Robert McCrae (1992) pointed out that the Big Five—five dimensions—are used to characterize personality traits. Openness to Experience, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism are the Big Five personality traits clusters that appear to reliably describe the core personality feature. Many previous studies also have focused on personality traits as a potential predictor of problematic mobile phone use behaviours due to the influence of personality on interpersonal interactions (Eysenck, 1994).

It was found that nomophobia is prevalent among undergraduate students that 99.33% of them were suffering from high level of nomophobia (Bajaj, Hariharan, Kini, Kurnsteiner, Raabe, & Jagle, 2020). Consequent upon all these, this study therefore examined the degree to which peer pressure and personality traits were responsible for the respondents' varied Nomophobic behaviour.

The majority of today's undergraduate students are using their smartphones as a medium of social interaction, research, sharing ideas, schoolwork or artistic creation. However, despite the myriad importance of smartphones in the world of education, undergraduate students seem to exhibit nomophobia whenever they are parted with this gadget. At the same time, undergraduate students are being exposed through this smartphone to the extent of becoming addicted, which is defining and redefining their psychosocial behaviours. There is no doubt that Nomophobic behaviour frequently disrupts smooth learning of the students which may result in poor academic performance and unusual behaviours. It places the undergraduate students' life at risk and makes culture of learning very difficult. Students might be having behavioural problems as a result of nomophobia and this is thought to be a leading contributor to students' stress, inability to learn and comprehend what the lecturer is teaching in the classroom.

Very often, such undergraduate students' life may be disrupted as a result of nomophobia. When Nomophobic behaviour is rampant in the school and society, there may be lack of effective control of students by lecturers during teaching and learning process, mood swing of the student and frustrations might set in. Depression might come into student's life

when there is no access to internet. The problem of fear, anxiety, down within the mind and body could be reduced if the students possess the ability to control their emotions whenever their smartphones are not available for use.

The main purpose of the study was to determine personality traits, peer influence as a correlates of Nomophobia behaviour among undergraduate students. Specifically, an attempt was made to:

- Investigate the prevalence of Nomophobic behaviour among undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria;
- Ascertain the correlates of each of the students' psychosocial factors (peer influence, personality traits) and Nomophobic behaviour among undergraduates;

1.1. Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were generated and tested in the study:

- There is no significant correlation between students' personality traits (agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness, extraversion and neuroticism) and Nomophobic behaviour among the undergraduate students.
- There is no significant correlation between peer influence and Nomophobic behaviour.

2. Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population for this study comprised undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU) in Ile-Ife, Osun State, Nigeria, in Southwestern geopolitical zone. A sample of 1040 undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University was selected using multistage sampling technique. Six faculties out of 13 were randomly selected using simple random sampling technique and two departments were selected from each of the six faculties using simple random sampling technique to give a total of 12 departments in all. Convenient sampling technique was used to select 90 (100 level to 400/500 level) students from each of the two departments selected in each faculty to make a total of 1080 respondents in all.

In carrying out this study, one research instrument titled "Psychosocial and Nomophobic Behaviour among Undergraduate students" (PNBUS) This instrument contained two sections. Nomophobia Questionnaire (NMP-Q) adopted from the original work of Yildirim & Correia Peer Influence Questionnaire (PIQ) adopted from Miller and Brown (2013), Big Five Personality questionnaire (BFI) adopted from Rammstedt and John (2007). The description of the instrument is as follows:

The first instrument was Nomophobia Questionnaire (NMP-Q). It comprised 20 items which were adopted from the research work of Yildirim & Corretia (2015), which contained 20 items originally. Therefore, the original psychometric properties comprised four factors (Factor 1: not being able to communicate; Factor 2: losing connectedness; Factor 3: not being able to access information; and Factor 4: giving up convenience). The four-factor structured among the 20 items instrument was supported in an exploratory factor analysis. The Cronbach's alpha was excellent across the entire NMP-Q ($\alpha = 0.94$) and each in each factor ($\alpha = 0.81-0.93$). Concurrent validity was achieved through its high correlation with Mobile Phone Involvement Questionnaire (MPIQ; $r = 0.71$; Yidirim & Correia, 2015). The overall Cronbach's alpha coefficient was 0.89 while 0.84 was gotten by the researcher and this value was considered adequate enough to guarantee reliability coefficient for the study. Meanwhile, no item was dropped after validation; the items were considered effective enough for the study because they were all reliable. The respondents were asked to tick the degree or option that best described them. The items were rated on a four-point Likert rating scale of 'Strongly Agree' (SA). 'Agree', (A) 'Disagree' (D) and 'Strongly Disagree' (SD) which was coded 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. Some items in the negative forms were given reversed scoring in order to be consistent with the scoring pattern. Three examples of items on the scale are: ('Running out of battery on my smartphone would scare me', 'I feel lonely without my smartphones', 'I feel anxious whenever I could not check my email messages'). The maximum and minimum scores obtained for academic engagement were 40 and 12 respectively. Higher score indicated that the respondent possessed Nomophobic behaviour while lower score indicated that the respondent lack Nomophobic behaviour.

The second instrument Peer Influence Questionnaire (PIQ) comprised 15 items adopted from Miller & Brown (2013) Peer Influence Questionnaire, all the items were found relevant to the Peer Influence Questionnaire. The statements were rated on a four Likert rating scale of strongly Agree (SA) scored 4, Agree (A) scored 3, Disagree (D) scored 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) scored 1, of which were coded 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. Three examples of items on the scale are: "I and my friends are always punctual in school, I have done dangerous and foolish things because friends dared me to and I usually do what I am told by my friends. The maximum and minimum scores were 64 and 14 respectively.

Higher score indicated that university undergraduate students were influenced by peers in doing things while lower score indicated that undergraduates were not influence in doing things.

The last instrument Big Five Personality (BFI) was measured using the 10-item short version of the Big Five Personality Traits, which was developed by Rammstedt and John (2007). The personality dimension measures are extraversion (sociable vs. reserve), agreeableness (trusting vs suspicious), conscientiousness (organised vs disorganised), neuroticism (anxious vs calm) and openness to experience (prefers variety vs. prefers routine) (Costa & McCrae, 1985). Items 1 and 5 measured the sub-domain of extraversion, item 2 and 7R measured the dimension of agreeableness, item 3R and 8 measured the domain of conscientiousness. Items 4R and 9 measured the domain of neuroticism, while items 5R and 10 measured the domain of openness to experience. The R means that items are reversed-scored. The scale used a response format of a four-point scale ranging from Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD), which were coded 4, 3, 2, and 1 correspondingly, Samples of the items on the scale read "I see myself as someone who tends to find fault with others." and "I see myself as someone who has an active imagination." High scores on any of these traits meant high traits, while low scores on any of these traits indicate low traits. The authors reported a Cronbach's alpha for the overall BFI scale as 0.80. There was also a Cronbach's alpha for each of the sub-scales as 0.73 for extraversion, 0.78 for agreeableness, 0.75 for conscientiousness, 0.77 for neuroticism, and 0.62 for openness to experience.

The instruments were validated by the use of rating scale and external validity. The instrument was given to experts in Psychology of Education, Guidance and Counseling and Tests and Measurement. They were of the opinion that the instrument contained the appropriate constructs and each item in the instrument is related to the construct in the research topic. The reliability coefficient of the sub-scale used in Section B titled Nomophobic Behaviour Questionnaire was 0.84, using Cronbach Alpha. Also, the reliability of the coefficient of sub- scale used in Section C titled Peer Influence Questionnaire was 0.83, using Cronbach Alpha. In addition, the reliability of coefficient of sub-scale used Section D titled Big Five Personality Questionnaire was 0.80, using the Cronbach Alpha coefficient. These values were considered significant enough to ascertain the reliability of the instrument.

3. Results

To test the hypotheses adequately, descriptive analysis was used for the interpretation of data and discussion of results. The result is presented in Table 1

Table 1a Mean Score and Standard deviation of Nomophobic behaviour

	N	Minimum	Maximum	\bar{X}	SD
Nomophobic behaviour	1040	20	78	47.24	10.21

The Table 1a shows the mean and standard deviation of Nomophobic behaviour. The minimum score on the scale is 20 while the maximum score is 78 with a mean of 47.24 and Standard deviation of 10.21

Table 1b Prevalence of Nomophobic behaviour

Attitude	Score Range	Frequency	Percentage
Low	20 -37	35	3.4
Moderate	38 – 56	872	83.8
High	57-78	133	12.8

The analysis revealed that 35(3.4%) of the participant have low prevalence of Nomophobic behaviour, 872(83.8%) of the participants have moderate prevalence of nomphobic behaviour while 133(12.8) of the respondents reported high prevalence of Nomophobic behaviour. Therefore, it was established that majority of the respondents have moderate prevalence of Nomophobic behaviour.

Hypothesis one: There is no significant correlation between students' personality traits (agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness, extraversion and neuroticism) and Nomophobic behaviour among undergraduate

students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. The hypothesis was tested using Zero-order correlation and the result is presented on Table 2.

Table 2 Zero order correlation between personality traits (agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness, extraversion and neuroticism) and Nomophobic behaviour

Variables	\bar{X}	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6 df
1. Extraversion	4.23	1.36	1					
2. Agreeableness	4.39	0.97	0.37**	1				
3. Conscientiousness	4.58	1.16	0.49**	0.72**	1			
4. Neuroticism	4.13	1.28	-0.19**	0.12**	-0.07*	1		
5. Openness to experience	4.51	1.34	0.30**	0.31**	0.43**	.00	1	
6. Nomophobic behaviour	47.24	10.21	0.04	0.12**	0.13**	0.26**	-0.01	1038

The result presented in Table 2 showed that there was no significant correlation between extraversion and Nomophobic behaviour [$r(1038) = .04, p > .05$]. The result also showed that there was a significant positive relationship between agreeableness and Nomophobic behaviour [$r(1038) = .12, p < .01$]. This implies that undergraduate students with high agreeableness tend to engage in high levels of Nomophobic behaviour. There was also a significant positive association between conscientiousness and Nomophobic behaviour [$r(1038) = .13, p < .01$]. The results indicate that undergraduate students who reported high level of conscientiousness tend to engage in increased Nomophobic behaviour. There was also significant correlation between neuroticism and Nomophobic behaviour [$r(1038) = 0.26, p < .01$]. This implies that undergraduates who reported high level of neuroticism tend to have increased Nomophobic behaviour. Also, there was no significant relationship between openness to experience and Nomophobic behaviour [$r(1038) = -.01, p > .05$]. The hypothesis which stated that there was no significant correlation between students' personality traits (agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness, extraversion and neuroticism) and Nomophobic behaviour was rejected while the alternate hypothesis that stated that there was significant correlation between students' personality traits (agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness, extraversion and neuroticism) and Nomophobic behaviour was accepted.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant correlation between peer influence and Nomophobic behaviour among undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria. The hypothesis was tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and the result was presented on Table 3

Table 3 Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) showing correlation between Peer influence and Nomophobic behaviour

	Variables	\bar{X}	SD	N	1	2	P	df
1	Peer influence	37.20	6.61	1040	-			
2	Nomophobic behaviour	47.24	10.21	1040	0.18**	-	<.05	1038

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The result presented in Table 3 showed that there was a significant positive correlation between peer influence and Nomophobic behaviour [$r(1038)=0.18, p < .01$]. The result implies that increase in peer influence among undergraduate students tends to increase in Nomophobic behaviour. The hypothesis which stated that there was no significant correlation between peer influence and Nomophobic behaviour among undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University was rejected while the alternate hypothesis which stated that there was significant relationship between peer influence and Nomophobic behaviour among undergraduate students of Obafemi Awolowo University was accepted.

4. Discussions

It was discovered that there was moderate prevalence rate of Nomophobic behaviour among the study population because 83.4% of undergraduate students exhibited the behaviour. In view of this, it could be as a result of too much

dependance on phones for daily and academic activities. Therefore, the results were in line with Mail Online (2008) who found that surveyed participants exhibited more Nomophobic behaviours. Furthermore, in agreement with SecurEnvoy (2012) it was discovered that there was a high prevalence of Nomophobic behaviour among British adults. Also, King et al., (2014); Sharma, Sharma, Sharma and Wavare (2015); Tavolacci, Meyrignac, Richard, Dechelotte and Ladner (2015) all found that majority of respondents exhibited high Nomophobic behaviour.

Gezgin and Adnan (2016) also reported similar findings and found that the severity of nomophobia is above average. Furthermore, the result was also in line with Ayar et al. (2018) who were of the opinion that Nomophobic behaviour was a common problem among nursing students, which contributed to its moderate prevalence. In contrary to the finding, it was established by Yildirim et al. (2016) that Nomophobic behaviours was not really common among university students because only 42.6% of them demonstrated it.

The first hypothesis showed that there was no significant relationship between extraversion and Nomophobic behaviour, there was significant positive relationship between agreeableness and Nomophobic behaviour. There was also a significant positive association between conscientiousness and Nomophobic behaviour. There was also significant correlation between neuroticism and Nomophobic behaviour. also, there was no significant relationship between openness to experience and Nomophobic behaviour. In view of this, it could be as a result of differences in student psychology that influences their behavioural patterns. Therefore, the study finding corresponds with Olapoju (2020), who found that there was a significant relationship between personality traits and nomophobia. The study finding was in line with Nalini, Mallya, Siddaling and Kumar (2018) who found that extraversion had a positive relationship with nomophobia. However, Tomsik (2018) was of the view that conscientiousness was positively related to Nomophobic behaviour. Also in the same result direction, Butt & Phillips, (2008); Ehrenberg et al., (2008) showed that individuals with a high score on neuroticism spent more time using their mobile phone for texting. Also, Lee et al. (2013) attributed to the fact that neurotic individuals preferred using text messaging as a way to cope with the anxiety induced by face-to-face interactions.

The result of the second hypothesis showed that there was a significant positive correlation between peer influence and Nomophobic behaviour. As regard to this, this could be as a result of positive influence that peer group has on the exposure of individual undergraduate students. The finding of the study therefore was in line with Salami and Salami (2013) who found that peer influence predicted nomophobic behaviour among students. Omotere (2011) indicated that peer group predicts students' performance. Poteat et al (2015) found that individuals, who are in a Nomophobic and aggressive peer groups, also engage in Nomophobic and aggressive behaviour. Contrary to this, WANG et.al (2017) who found that peer relationship was significantly negatively associated with adolescent smartphone addiction. Jo and Bang (2021) found a significant effect on peer relationships, depression, and smartphone addiction. Zhao Ye and Yu (2021) was of the opinion that peer group was positively associated with smartphone.

5. Conclusion

In view of the finding from the study, it can therefore be concluded that a large percentage of undergraduate students in Obafemi Awolowo University exhibited Nomophobia. 83.4% of the participants found to exhibit a moderate level prevalence of Nomophobic behaviour. Female undergraduate students have been found to exhibit nomophobia than their male counterparts but this difference is not significant. The students' correlation to nomophobia is influenced by peer influence and personality traits. It was recommended that Parents, teachers and other stakeholders who form the agents of socialization should encourage the undergraduate students to neutralize their relationship with the use of phone so that they will be free from Nomophobic tendencies.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

The present research work does not contain any studies performed on animals/humans subjects by any of the authors.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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